

Siberian Regionalism and Eurasianism: Complicated Relationships

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ABSTRACT

Igor V. Likhomanov. *Siberian Regionalism and Eurasianism: Complicated Relationships.* Siberian regionalism movement is discussed in the paper in relation to classical Eurasianism of the 1920s. The political differences between Siberian regionalism and Eurasianism were by no means accidental. They were a consequence of deep theoretical differences. The Siberian regional concept was based on the idea of Siberia as a separate economic and geographical region, completely different in its natural and climatic conditions from the European part of Russia. The regionalists focussed on the geographical originality of Russian Siberia, as well as its remoteness and isolation from the "metropolitan state" in geographic and economic terms. All this fundamentally contradicted the "Eurasian geography," which as persistently smoothed out the geographical space of Russia, trying to present it more homogeneous than it really was. The mental maps of the regionalists and Eurasians did not coincide on the basic level: they both saw the geographic space of Russia in different ways, just as they perceived the structure of its economy. The analysis performed in the article may help to evaluate ideological foundations of modern Eurasian political blocks and alliances as well as Eurasian international legal initiatives.

Key words: Eurasianism, Siberian regionalism, Siberia, Far East, nomadic society, settled society

M. N. SHILOVSKY (1999) WAS THE FIRST to raise the question of the attitude of Siberian regionalism to Eurasianism in his article “Siberian Roots of Eurasianism”. Shilovsky answered this question in a positive sense, pointing out the similarity of some ideas of the Siberian regionalists with ideas of the Eurasian thinkers. However, his conclusion that the fundamental ideas of Eurasians of the early 1920s had been developed long before by Siberian regionalists, was too strong and, therefore, it raised reasonable objections. In 2007, Tomsk-based researcher S. V. Seliverstov (2007) returned to this problem and advanced a hypothesis that there were two trends in the Siberian regionalism. One, presented by N. M. Yadrintsev, transformed into pure Westernism, and the other, presented by G. N. Potanin, led to the emergence of a special type of “practical” Eurasianism, which had some significant differences from the “ideological” Eurasianism of the twentieth century.

Thanks to M. N. Shilovsky and S. V. Seliverstov, the topic of interrelation between Siberian regionalism and Eurasianism was included in the comprehensive scientific discourse. However, the collective monograph *The Eurasian World: Values, Constants, Self-Organisation* (Popkov 2010), which has an extensive section on the genesis of Eurasianism, completely overlooked this topic. The authors of the monograph representing academic neo-Eurasianism are likely to demonstrate that they do not consider Siberian region thinkers as their ideological predecessors. The demonstrative rejection of any “kinship” is a remarkable fact, but it strengthens wide scientific interest to a problem which retains its scientific relevance due to a wide range of opinions. In this article, I shall offer an analysis that differs as well from Drs Shilovskiy and Seliverstov’s points of view as from the opinion tacitly expressed by representatives of academic neo-Eurasianism.

The refusal of modern neo-Eurasianists to see in Siberian regionalists the predecessors of the “classical” Eurasianism of the 1920s has reasonable grounds. Regionalism emerged in the early 1860s as a populist and revolutionary, purely democratic trend of social thought. Subsequently, the revolutionary spirit of regionalism faded away in Russia, and it turned into a regional offspring of liberal populism close to the right wing of the Socialist Revolutionary Party, “with significant intersperses of Enlightenment approach” (Shilovsky 2008, 95). This Enlightenment-, essentially “Westernising”-related and liberal-democratic character of the Siberian regionalism ideology contrasts sharply with the Eurasianist ideology of the 1920s. The Eurasianists were neither liberals, nor democrats, nor, moreover, Westernisers. They advocated a totalitarian and “ideocratic” state that combined some features of the “corporate state” of fascist Italy with some of the state built in the USSR. In addition, the Eurasians were isolationists who believed that between Russia and the West, on the one hand, and between Russia and the non-Muslim (Confucian-Buddhist) East, on the other, there were insurmountable cultural barriers. On the contrary, the Siberian regionalists emphasised universal character of the world culture.

However, Eurasianists and Siberian regionalists were most dissimilar in their attitude towards territorial-state structure of Russia. Regionalism arose as a separatist branch in Russian populism movement. Mainly for that reason its founders were sent to penal servitude and exile by the Russian Imperial government. Later the regionalists’ programme lost its

radicalism in this issue, but some separatist tendencies were persistent in the main ideology of the movement until the Revolution and Civil war. "Twice," M. N. Shilovsky (2008, 3) writes, "during the birth in the first half of the 1860s and the social cataclysms of 1917-1920, regionalism put forward a programme for the creation of state education in the East of Russia. But even in the period when the regional officials refused the idea of secession in favour of the autonomous state of Siberia, this autonomy, as they believed, looked more like a confederation than a federation. Such a viewpoint decisively contradicted the ideology of the Eurasianists who advocated a strong and centralised "ideocratic" state governed by a bureaucracy. This state was polyethnic in composition but endowed with a "common worldview." Extremely reluctantly and with great reservations, the leaders of Eurasianism admitted a federal structure of the future Russian state – it was just a consequence of the relevant *status quo*. But at the same time, they put forward a huge *Kulturträger* programme for the formation of a single Eurasian cultural space on Russian territory, aimed at "fusing" all national cultures into a single "Eurasian culture," and all peoples living in Russia into a single "multinational nation." If realised, such a programme would have cancelled the core meaning of federalism.

It is important to understand that the political differences between Siberian regionalism and Eurasianism were by no means accidental. They were a consequence of deep theoretical differences. The Siberian regional concept was based on the idea of Siberia as a separate economic and geographical region, completely different in its natural and climatic conditions from the European part of Russia. The regionalists focussed on the geographical originality of Siberia, as well as its remoteness and isolation from the "metropolitan state" in geographic and economic terms. All this fundamentally contradicted the "Eurasian geography," which as persistently smoothed out the geographical space of Russia, trying to present it more homogeneous than it really was. The mental maps of the regionalists and Eurasians did not coincide on the basic level: they both saw the geographic space of Russia in different ways, just as they perceived the structure of its economy.

With all that said, what were the grounds for M. N. Shilovsky and S. V. Seliverstov to assert that the Siberian regionalists were ideological predecessors of the Eurasianists or even the first Russian Eurasianists? Dr Shilovsky provides four arguments proving his view. First, Siberian regionalists changed their viewpoint on the Russian history in an innovative way, not "from the West to East" (a common historiographical tradition), but "from the East to West", as the Eurasians later did. Second, they formed the idea of "the determining influence of natural and climatic factors on the development of individual peoples," which is also a distinctive characteristic of the Eurasian social concept. Third, regionalists announced the formation of a specific "Siberian nation" beyond the Urals, which presumably was a result of mixing Slavs with Finno-Ugrians and Turks. In this regard, they anticipated the idea of the Eurasianists about the presence of a special "Eurasian nation." Finally, they (as G. N. Potanin did) formulated an hypothesis about an eastern (Eurasian) origin of not only Slavic culture, but also Western European culture, European epic, Christian religion, etc.

All four arguments of Dr Shilovsky, however, do not seem so obvious and straightforward

to accept them uncritically. Siberian regionalists formed their vision of Russian history on the basis of the dilemma “colony – metropolitan state.” Indeed, it was a view “from the East to West,” but only from the Russian East to the Russian West. It had nothing in common with the Eurasianist approach to Russian history, where the presence of the united Eurasian space as a place of a large-scale historical action was postulated. In this place, the participants, individuals and nations, interacting with each other, were allegedly involved in a complex and multifaceted process of cultural synthesis. In other words, the Eurasianists looked at the history of Russia “from the East to West: not in the sense in which Siberian regionalists did it.

The second argument can be taken into account even less, since the regionalists were in no way geographic determinists, in contrast to the Eurasianists. For the latter, the stratagem of “locality” was of fundamental importance. Recognising the role of the geographic factor in the economic and socio-cultural development of various regions, neither G. N. Potanin, nor N. M. Yadrintsev gave it a defining or conceptual meaning as it has in Eurasianism.

The most difficult is the analysis of the third argument. It seems obvious that the “Eurasian nation” introduced by the Eurasianists is an analogue of the “Siberian nation” whose concept was elaborated by the Siberian regionalists. Such a “nation” allegedly arose as a result of ethno-cultural mixing of the Slavs with the Finno-Ugrians and Turks. In other words, what the regionalists “discovered” in Siberia (the process of ethno-cultural synthesis), the “classical” Eurasians of the 1920s “rediscovered” for the entire population of the former Russian Empire. However, this striking similarity should not mislead us.

The regionalists started from the idea of the ethno-cultural diversity of the population of the Russian Empire, including the Great Russians. An idea predecessor of the regionalists was N. N. Kostomarov, whose federalist ideas would be assimilated by regionalists and ingeniously applied to the analysis of ethno-cultural processes in Siberia. Besides, Kostomarov focussed on the ethno-cultural diversity of the Great Russian people. According to Kostomarov, the Great Russian people as a single ethno-cultural entity did not exist at all. In fact, “Great Russians,” in his opinion, is only a general name for a number of smaller ethnic groups (sub-ethnoses), either autochthonous or formed as a result of genetic and ethno-cultural mixing of Slavs with non-Slavic peoples.

On the basis of these ideas as well as thoughts of A. P. Shchapov, who was the first to describe the process of the Eurasian ethno-cultural synthesis in Siberia, N. M. Yadrintsev developed the concept of creating the “Siberian nationality” of the population of central Russia. Distinctive features of the anthropological type, mentality, way of life, economic and social conditions of life of Siberians were intended to confirm the Yadrintsev’s idea about the formation of a special Eurasian and the “Siberian nationality.” In the political dimension, it was supposed to form the foundation for justifying the political demand for independence (or, at least, a broad autonomy) of Siberia from the Russian centre.

Focussing attention on the cultural and anthropological differences between a Siberian “Eurasian” from a “pure” Slav, a Great Russian (and even artificially “condensing” these

differences), N. M. Yadrintsev tried to support the argumentation of the regionalists, which was based mainly on geographical and economic grounds heretofore. It is not difficult to notice that his cognitive attitude, a sharp opposition of Siberian “Eurasians” as an ethno-cultural entity to the “pure” Great Russians, Slavs, contradicted the idea of the Eurasianists aimed at integrating Russia into a single political and sociocultural space based on the notion of Eurasian ethno-cultural unity of the entire population of Eurasia.

Nevertheless, M. N. Shilovsky is right when he considers the concept of the “Siberian nationality” in the context of the Eurasian discourse from an Eurasian perspective. However, it should be noted that Siberian regionalists were not the first to pay attention to the phenomenon of Eurasian ethno-cultural melting. N. V. Gogol and N. N. Kostomarov wrote about this phenomenon a lot. They believed that the Ukrainian ethnos arose as a result of mixing the Slavs of the ancient Russian South with the Turks, and the Great Russian as a result of mixing the Northeast Slavs with the Finno-Ugric peoples. The author of the “Turanian theory” of the origin of Russians, Frantisek Dukhinsky also wrote about this. Regionalists, mainly A. P. Shchapov and N. M. Yadrintsev, should be credited in their bringing the problem of Eurasian ethno-cultural synthesis to the forefront of scientific attention.

There is another important ideological heritage of the Siberian regionalists that was not paid due attention to by M. N. Shilovsky. It obviously lies in the mainstream of the Eurasian tradition. Regionalists were the first in Russian social thought to radically change the attitude towards nomadic cultures and peoples. Before them, Russian historiography was dominated by a hostile and contemptuous attitude towards the nomads. In the mainstream of the tradition coming from Hegel, the nomadic peoples were viewed by Russian academicians as “non-historical,” i.e. playing a role of a “God’s scourge”. The mainstream Russian historians considered them as a hostile “primitive” force that hindered the development of Rus for many hundred years (e.g. within the concept of the struggle between “forest and steppe” advanced by the Russian historian S. M. Solovyov).

In 1891, N. M. Yadrintsev published his article “The Significance of Nomadic Life in the History of Human Culture,” where for the first time, at least in Russian social thought, he presented a different point of view on nomadic cultures. First, he considered nomadic civilisation as a separate stage in the development of mankind with its own internal evolution. Second, he drew attention to the inner wealth and diversity of nomadic cultures, which, in his opinion, reached a very high level precisely in the field of spiritual creativity. “A nomad,” wrote Yadrintsev (2000, vol. 2, 271), “began to possess spare time that gave him an opportunity to philosophise, create, developed a rich imagination, encouraged dreaminess and formed poetry; nomadic tribes are very melodious, their myths and tales are rich in imagination as well as in morality.” In the process of its evolution, in the end nomadic culture reaches perfection, beyond which there is nowhere to go. Here Yadrintsev obviously approaches the concept in cultural studies that is characteristic of both Eurasians and Western anthropologists of the twentieth century. According to the concept, the degree of perfection and elaboration of a particular culture has no relation to the level of the technological development of the people that possesses the culture.

Finally, in the historical drama of the struggle of the nomadic Asian peoples with the sedentary peoples of Eastern and Western Europe, Yadrintsev did not in the least see a struggle of civilisation against barbarism. Instead, he found a positive meaning in it. "Resettlement and movement of peoples from the East," he wrote, "should be considered not in the sense of Barbarian invasion, but as the beginning of cultural rapprochement and exchange of the East with the West" (Ibid, 270). In particular, he implies cultural exchange between the "rich sedentary cultures and civilisations" of Turan (Fergana, Bukhara, Turkestan) and peoples of Eastern and Western Europe through the mediation of Asian steppe nomads.

The ideas of N. M. Yadrintsev were developed by G. N. Potanin in his works devoted to the study of folklore of the nomadic peoples of Siberia, Central Asia and the Far East. He put forward a hypothesis that the medieval Western European epic and folklore were formed under the powerful influence of the epic and folklore of the nomadic Asian peoples invading the territory of Eastern and Western Europe, from ancient times to the thirteenth century. In ancient times, Potanin believed, the world of Eurasia was a single "huge workshop from France to Mongolia," where, thanks to the constant movement of Asian nomadic tribes from East to West and in the opposite direction, there was a continuous cultural exchange.

It is important to stress that in this regard the views of the Siberian regionalists are radically different from those of the Eurasians. For both Yadrintsev and Potanin, world culture is a single culture, where there is a free exchange of various components and where the East does not oppose the West, and the West does not oppose the East. Yes, in ancient times, the East, in their opinion, had a deep influence on the formation of Western cultures. Now the time has come when the West has pulled ahead and causes a reciprocal beneficial effect on the peoples of the East. Meanwhile, there is nothing more contrary to the Eurasian thought than the idea of the unity of the world culture. All the pathos, all the fire of Eurasian criticism was aimed at destroying this notion, depicting humanity divided into isolated and hostile cultural and anthropological enclaves, in the centre of which is Russia-Eurasia that was constantly opposing both "insatiable greed" and egocentrism of Europe and the "satanic temptations" of the Confucian-Buddhist East, where the devil "made his own nest." Therefore, to interpret the Potanin-Yadrintsev concept within the boundaries of the modern academic neo-Eurasianism, as S. V. Seliverstov does, and to integrate it into pre-Eurasian discourse is incorrect. It is just as wrong as opposing the views of the "Westernizer" Yadrintsev to the views of the "Eurasianist" Potanin.

The far-fetched problem of N. M. Yadrintsev's "turn" from pre-Eurasian discourse to Westernism, that was in his pre-mortem several years, may be resolved in the context of the regionalists' perception of the unity of world culture. "Western culture and civilisation attracted the Russian educated person not because it is Western and European," Yadrintsev (1979, 215) argued, "Western and European culture is in fact the culture of all mankind and the world. There is no other culture and civilisation." As one can see, Yadrintsev makes a special emphasis here on the fact that European culture is a "common human affair," i.e. it is a result of the global synthesis, at least within the boundaries of the Old World, covering

two continents, Africa and Eurasia. And in this sense, it may be considered a vanguard of this common world culture, pulling along all other peoples and cultures. But a single world culture also has an opposite pole, rearguard, which is represented by undeveloped Asian countries. Russia, as a “semi-Asian state,” is at a historical crossroads, to follow the vanguard or roll back into the rearguard of the world culture. With such formulating the question, the answer is obvious. By the beginning of the 1890s, Yadrintsev, experiencing a deep mental crisis caused not only by his personal hardships in life, but also political reaction, believed in the future of Russia no longer.

Potanin, who shared his friend’s pessimism only partially, did not disagree with him in the general conceptual view of the world history. His enthusiasm for the nomadic cultures of Siberia, Central Asia and the Far East was aimed at revealing their originality and wealth included in the general context of the world culture. In no way he opposed the East and the West as the two worlds hostile to each other.

S. V. Seliverstov’s hypothesis about two trends in regionalism, Westernising and Eurasian, has its origin in the fact that the researcher compares these views not with the “classical” Eurasianism of the 1920s and 1930s, but with the current, conceptually blurred views of representatives of Russian academic and political neo-Eurasianism. This is obvious from his statement that Potanin’s concept of the decisive influence of the “Eastern Horde” epic on the West European is purely Eurasian, “since its main meaning is not in the separation of the European West, Russia and the Asian East, but in their ancient cultural and historical unity” (Seliverstov 2007, 111). But purely Eurasian point of view is opposite to this statement. Moreover, even in modern neo-Eurasianism, the isolationist tendency prevails over the universalist one, although it does not exclude the latter, as it was classical Eurasianism.

Summing up the results, we can draw the following conclusion: the inclusion of Siberian regionalism in the context of pre-Eurasian discourse is justified only in two aspects.

Firstly, it is possible in the sense that regionalists were the first in Russian social thought to choose the processes of Eurasian ethno-cultural synthesis as a subject of scientific discourse. Secondly, the regionalists made a revolutionary turn in the views on the nomadic cultures and peoples of Eurasia, as well as on their role in the world history. This ideas was subsequently appropriated and developed by the Eurasianists. The question of whether there was a direct continuity in the views of the Eurasianists and Siberian regionalists (in other words, whether the Eurasianists were familiar with the main ideas of regionalists when they formulated provisions of their own theory) requires additional study. At the same time, it is obvious that Siberian regionalism as a branch of socio-political thought was completely dissimilar to Eurasianism.

The relationships between the two branches of Russian social thought discussed in the paper are not relationships of kinship or similarity. They are obviously too complicated to be presented as a simple logical or genetic succession.

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EXTENDED SUMMARY

LIKHOMANOV, IGOR V. DAWNING OF A NEW DARK AGE? SIBERIAN REGIONALISM AND EURASIANISM: COMPLICATED RELATIONSHIPS.

EURASIANISM IS WIDELY KNOWN AS AN INTERDISCIPLINARY SOCIAL AND CULTURAL MOVEMENT that has arisen in Russia in 1920s and was based on the idea of Eurasian historical, legal and political unity. Siberian regionalism is much less spoken of in scholar circles, whether Russian or foreign, remaining a narrow branch of social thought for the majority of researchers. In the current work, I analyse complicated relationships between the two scientific movements towards Eurasia to assess their value for studying transformation processes of Eurasia taking place both in the past and in the present.

The relationships between the two branches of Russian social thought dis-

cussed in the paper are not relationships of kinship or similarity. They are obviously too complicated to be presented as a simple logical or genetic succession.

The paper presents critical analysing the viewpoints of two researchers that have recently returned scientific interest to Siberian regionalism, M. N. Shilovsky and S. V. Seliverstov. It is noteworthy that the collective monograph *The Eurasian World: Values, Constants, Self-Organisation*, which has an extensive section on the genesis of Eurasianism, completely overlooked the topic of Siberian regionalism. The authors of the monograph representing academic neo-Eurasianism are likely to demonstrate that they do not consider Siberian region thinkers as their ideological predecessors. The demonstrative rejection of any "kinship" is a remarkable fact, but it strengthens wide scientific interest to Siberian regionalism and its relation to Eurasianism. In the current paper, I am analysing the problem from a different viewpoint than Drs Shilovskiy and Seliverstov's as well as the opinion expressed by representatives of academic neo-Eurasianism in the aforementioned collective monograph.

Concepts of the following Siberian regionalists are studied in the paper based on investigating rare, mainly archival sources: N. M. Yadrintsev, G. N. Potanin, A. P. Shchapov. Besides, ethno-cultural theories of N. V. Gogol, N. N. Kostomarov and Frantisek Dukhinsky are reconstructed and analysed in the context of their connection with Siberian regional theory.

It is proven that we cannot consider Siberian regionalists as predecessors of classical Eurasianists of the first half of the twentieth century. "Westernising"-related and liberal-democratic character of the Siberian regionalism ideology contrasts sharply with the Eurasianist ideology of the 1920s. The Eurasianists were neither liberals, nor democrats, nor, moreover, Westernisers. They advocated a totalitarian and "ideocratic" state that combined some features of the "corporate state" of fascist Italy with some of the state built in the USSR. In addition, the Eurasians were isolationists who believed that between Russia and the West, on the one hand, and between Russia and the non-Muslim (Confucian-Buddhist) East, on the other, there were insurmountable cultural barriers. On the contrary, the Siberian regionalists emphasised universal character of the world culture.

Focussing attention on the cultural and anthropological differences between a Siberian "Eurasian" from a "pure" Slav, a Great Russian (and even artificially "condensing" these differences), N. M. Yadrintsev tried to support the argumentation of the Siberian regionalists, which was based mainly on geographical and economic grounds heretofore. The cognitive attitude of this classic of the nineteenth century, i.e. the sharp opposition of the Siberian "Eurasians" as an ethno-cultural entity to the "pure" Great Russians, Slavs, contradicted the idea of the Eurasianists aimed at integrating Russia into a single political and sociocultural space based on the notion of Eurasian ethno-cultural unity of the entire population of Eurasia.

The works of Siberian regionalists are important for understanding not only centrifugal and centripetal socio-political tendencies of the late nineteenth – early twentieth centuries in Russian Empire and later USSR, but also modern ways and routes of developing Eurasia, including Eurasian political alliances and international agreements within Eurasian space.

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